

THE INFLUENCE OF BEAUTY CONTENT, CONTEXT, AND CREATOR IN THE TIKTOK MARKETPLACE ON THE ENGAGEMENT OF MANILA CONSUMERS

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ABSTRACT

As TikTok continues to flourish, understanding it as a digital marketplace requires further empirical inquiry. Given this, the current study aims to understand the influence of TikTok content, context, and creators on consumer engagement, particularly in the beauty industry. The information gathered from 398 Manila consumers, with a specific focus on those who have experienced buying beauty products in TikTok, was gathered using a survey and analyzed using Spearman's correlation analysis. The study's findings reveal that three independent variables, namely TikTok contents, contexts, and creators, significantly and positively influence the engagement of Manila consumers in the beauty industry.

Keywords: *customer engagement, beauty industry, TikTok marketing, content, creator*

INTRODUCTION

In this modern time, individuals have been hooked on using various social media platforms for entertainment. Despite the use of social media for this purpose, several studies have been conducted to determine their use as a digital marketing tool. For instance, in Jaakonmäki et al.'s (2017) study about the impact of social media marketing on user engagement, 96 percent of their 3,700 respondents reported utilizing different social media platforms for business. The same author reported that people are familiar with various social media engagements, especially with popular applications, which help consumers look for affordable products that they can use.

According to Farook and Abeysekara (2016), getting people to notice brand posts and encouraging them to engage with the material is a concern for a business. Engagements through social media are often measured by the number of likes and comments on posts (Chen et al., 2023) and user growth like followers and subscribers (Balbi et al., 2018). It is better if each of these indicators has a higher volume. Even though some posts do not receive too many likes, there is still a chance that they will influence people and have an unexpected impact on users in the future. Some posts may not have the full context, but it is one of the reasons why customers are curious about the content and look it up on the internet, making it part of their feed through the algorithm. With this, knowing the various interests and preferences of consumers helps in providing context for any social media postings made and improves communication with people.

One of the product lines flourishing through social media marketing is related to the beauty industry. Given the rise of beauty product advertisements on different social media platforms, many researchers have endeavored to investigate its influence on consumer behavior. For instance, in the study of Syawaluddin et al. (2019), three variables, namely social media marketing, e-marketing, and product quality, are identified as positive and significant factors influencing consumer's decision on purchasing cosmetics. Their data findings support the imminent relevance of the use of social media in advertising beauty products on different online platforms. Moreover, several studies have focused on how social media platforms, such as Instagram, Facebook, and Twitter, are used as advertising channels to boost customer engagement with beauty products. One of these empirical endeavors is the study of Lauwrence et al. (2024), wherein the application of direct messages through Instagram is empirically validated to be an effective way to interact with the company's customers, increase brand loyalty, and strengthen customer engagement. However, a paucity of studies on the utilization of the TikTok marketplace for the same purpose has been identified.

In this light, the current study focuses on TikTok's features to expand the current knowledge on how social media creators of beauty products, context, and content affect Manila users' engagement. Moreover, it aims at empirically identifying the benefits of TikTok as a platform for promoting beauty products.

Research Questions

Since this study aims to determine the statistical influences of TikTok's content, context, and creators of beauty products on the engagement of Manila consumers, the following questions were sought:

1. How does TikTok's content help significantly increase Manila consumers' engagement with beauty products?
2. How does TikTok context significantly boost beauty products' Manila consumer engagement?
3. How do TikTok beauty creators' popularity and reputation significantly affect Manila consumers' engagement?

In relation to these questions, the following null hypotheses were tested:

H₀₁: TikTok content related to beauty products has no significant influence on the engagement of select Manila consumers.

- Ho₂*: TikTok contexts related to beauty products have no significant influence on the engagement of select Manila consumers.
- Ho₃*: TikTok beauty creators' popularity and reputation do not significantly influence the engagement of select Manila consumers.

Conceptual Framework

Following Jaakonmäki et al.'s (2017) drivers of social media engagement, the study employed three independent variables – contents, contexts, and creators, as factors influencing the engagement of Manila consumers in beauty products promoted in the TikTok marketplace. According to the same authors, user engagement can be significantly impacted by the kind and quality of content provided on social media. Relevant, educational, interesting, and aesthetically pleasing content will likely catch users' attention and develop engagement. Moreover, user engagement can be affected by the context in which social media material is shared. For instance, content shared with the appropriate audience at the appropriate moment, on the appropriate platform, can result in more significant interaction than content shared at the incorrect time or on the incorrect platform. User engagement may also be controlled by the social media content creator. Mostly loyal followers of influencers and celebrities can use their support to extend the reach of content and increase engagement.

Considering these drivers of social media engagement, Figure 1 serves as the study's research paradigm. The figure shows that the three identified drivers – TikTok contents, contexts, and creators, independently influence the level of engagement of select Manila consumers with beauty products.

Figure 1

Research Paradigm

In the study, content is operationally defined as the medium of a TikTok post. Following the model of Jaakonmaki et al. (2017), content is considered as either of the three types – textual content, visual content, and audio content. Additionally, context is defined as the

storyline or meaning of the posted content. Notably, content and context vary in every TikTok post, which may affect customer engagement positively or negatively. Lastly, creators significantly affect customer engagement due to the reason that they are visible to the consumers. Creators are also a major factor in consumer engagement since they interact with the audience (Jaakonmaki et al., 2017).

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This study employed correlational research to examine the relationships of beauty content, context, and creator in the TikTok marketplace with Manila consumer engagement. According to Cresswell (2012, as cited in Seeram, 2019), a correlational research design is a statistical test used to identify the relationship between two or more variables or sets of data. This design is considered, as it can be used to discover if the study's independent variables have significant influences on the customer engagement of select Manila consumers. Moreover, it is noteworthy that previous related studies like Jaakonmäki et al. (2017) and Darmatama and Erdiansyah (2021) utilized the same approach.

Sample and Sampling Technique

In this study, purposive sampling was used to determine the sample of Manila consumers that will be surveyed. According to Campbell et al. (2020), utilizing purposive sampling better matches the sample to the research goals and objectives, enhancing the study's rigor and the data's reliability. This sampling technique was conducted in this research to gather data from the most fitting and appropriate respondents. The following criteria were considered in the selection of the study's respondents: (1) must be 18-50 years old, (2) must be a user of TikTok, and (3) must be a consumer of beauty products/services. Through this sampling technique, 398 beauty consumers in Manila were included in the study. Using the G*Power software, this sample size exceeds the minimum required number of responses to determine a statistical effect in a bivariate correlational test (with a minimum sample size of $n=84$).

Data Gathering Procedure

This study utilized a self-developed survey questionnaire to collect data. The questionnaire comprises four-point Likert scale sub-questionnaires: consumer purchasing decisions, beauty products' TikTok content, beauty products' TikTok context, and beauty products' TikTok creator. An expert in the field of business administration validated the study's questionnaire. Before conducting the main study, the researchers conducted an internal and participatory pilot study to test and make changes to the research methods after receiving clearance from an ethics research committee. The

dataset collected from this pilot testing was used to check the reliability of the study's instrument using Cronbach's alpha. Since the resulting alphas all exceed 0.80, the four Likert scales were deemed internally consistent. Then, the actual data gathering transpired by administering the survey online.

Data Analysis

The study used quantitative strategies to analyze the data collected. The weighted means for each item and each scale were computed to describe the results of the Likert scales. Furthermore, Spearman's rho correlation test was used to identify the individual influences of the study's independent variables (TikTok beauty contents, contexts, and creators) on the engagement of Manila consumers. This mode identifies relations with two ranked variables and measures the data's strengths and direction. A positive correlation shows that the variables increase or decrease together, following each other. In contrast, a negative correlation shows that when one variable increases, the other decreases, and vice versa.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 1 shows the respondents' level of engagement with beauty products in TikTok using weighted means. The respondents generally agreed on all the items pertaining to consumers' level of engagement, as evidenced by the overall weighted mean of 3.08. Specifically, the statement "Based on my observations, TikTok is an effective platform for customer engagements on beauty products" received the highest agreement level among the respondents, with a weighted mean of 3.40. On the other hand, the statement "I go to TikTok to discover new beauty brand finds" obtained the lowest assessment level with a weighted mean of 2.95. These findings suggest that the select Manila consumers are highly engaged with content or creators related to beauty products in TikTok.

Table 1

Agreement Levels on Select TikTok Consumer Engagement

Indicator	Weighted Mean	Interpretation
1. My TikTok "For you page" consists of more than ten beauty product related videos in a day.	2.98	Agree
2. I go to TikTok to discover new beauty brand finds.	2.95	Agree
3. My engagement in TikTok with new beauty products has led me into purchasing those products.	2.97	Agree

4. Based on my observation, TikTok is an effective platform for customer engagement on beauty products.	3.40	Strongly Agree
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Overall Mean	3.08	Agree
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Note. The verbal interpretation is based on the following: Strongly disagree: 1.00-1.75; Disagree: 1.76-2.50; Agree: 2.51-3.25; Strongly Agree: 3.26-4.00.

Table 2 summarizes the respondents' agreement levels on select indicators about the influence of TikTok content on their engagement with beauty products. The respondents strongly agree on all indicators, evidenced by the overall weighted mean of 3.41. Specifically, the statement "Content (Textual, Visual, Audio) matters in customer engagement" received the highest agreement level, with a weighted mean of 3.62. On the other hand, the statement "I engage with a beauty content TikTok video if it is eye-pleasing disregarding the creator and context of the video" obtained the lowest assessment level, with a weighted mean of 3.17. Accordingly, these findings imply that, on average, the select Manila consumers appear to highly engage with beauty products in any form of TikTok content.

These findings relate to the study of Ansari et al. (2019), stating that healthy content helps deliver brand activities and engage with customers. Furthermore, the data results on the statement "I like engaging in TikTok content that contains a visual demonstration about a product," which garnered a 3.62 weighted mean, further validates the findings of Adobe's (2014) *The Social Intelligence Report*, stating that posts with visual content are the best engaging contents.

Table 2

Agreement Levels on Select Indicators of TikTok Content and Consumer Engagement

Indicator	Weighted Mean	Interpretation
1. I like engaging in TikTok content that contains a textual description about a product	3.29	Strongly Agree
2. I like engaging in TikTok content that contains an audio/voice-over description about the product.	3.44	Strongly Agree
3. I like engaging in TikTok content that contains a visual demonstration about a product.	3.61	Strongly Agree
4. When the text is appealing and high-quality, I engage in the TikTok video.	3.36	Strongly Agree
5. When I find appearances of people in a TikTok video, I engage with it.	3.35	Strongly Agree
6. When the audio is clear, relatable, and	3.46	Strongly Agree

catchy, I engage in the TikTok video.		
7. I engage with a beauty content TikTok video if it is eye-pleasing, disregarding the creator and context of the video.	3.17	Agree
8. Content (textual, visual, audio) matters in customer engagement.	3.62	Strongly Agree
Overall Mean	3.41	Strongly Agree

Note. The verbal interpretation is based on the following: Strongly disagree: 1.00-1.75; Disagree: 1.76-2.50; Agree: 2.51-3.25; Strongly Agree: 3.26-4.00.

Table 3 shows the respondents' assessment of context engagement using weighted means. The respondents mostly strongly agree on all items concerning context, as evidenced by the overall weighted mean of 3.29. Notably, the statement "Context matters in customer engagement" received the highest agreement from the respondents, with a weighted mean of 3.57. The following one, which received the second highest agreement from the respondents, the statement "I am most likely to engage with TikTok beauty posts about how effective the product is," received a weighted mean of 3.42. These results suggest that the context of posted content about beauty products in TikTok is a salient factor affecting the Manila consumers' level of engagement with said products. These outcomes are supported by Bilgin (2018), who states that having a good utility and knowing the use of a product from posts construct better consumer engagement. Correspondingly, these findings on context and engagement level verify the findings of the study of Jaakonmäki et al. (2017), which establish the salience of context in terms of increasing engagement level of consumers in products marketed in online domains.

Table 3

Agreement Levels on Select Indicators of TikTok Context and Consumer Engagement

Indicator	Weighted Mean	Interpretation
1. I am most likely to engage with posts that are about beauty product reviews.	3.09	Agree
2. I am most likely to engage with TikTok beauty posts that show and use beauty products for Get ready with me (GRWM) videos.	3.20	Agree
3. I am most likely to engage with TikTok beauty posts that compare and contrast two beauty products by product reviews.	3.19	Agree
4. I am most likely to engage with TikTok beauty posts about how effective the product is.	3.42	Strongly Agree
5. Context matters in customer engagement.	3.57	Strongly Agree

Overall Mean	3.29	Strongly Agree
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Note. The verbal interpretation is based on the following: Strongly disagree: 1.00-1.75; Disagree: 1.76-2.50; Agree: 2.51-3.25; Strongly Agree: 3.26-4.00.

Table 4 shows the respondents' agreement levels on select indicators of creators' influence on their engagement with beauty products in TikTok. They generally agree on all the items on the scale, as evidenced by the overall weighted mean of 3.10. Specifically, the statement "Creator's current issues greatly impact my engagement with them" received the highest agreement levels among the respondents, with a weighted mean of 3.33. On the other hand, the statement "If a beauty content creator has 5k+ followers, I will most likely engage with them even if it is the first time I have seen them" obtained the lowest assessment levels with a weighted mean of 2.83.

Within the context of value co-creation, Ren et al. (2022) highlight the importance of carefully examining how social media content creators interact with customers, influence one another, and promote community building in commercial promotion initiatives. As the above findings validate creators' influence on consumer engagement, this study supports the statement of Ren et al. (2022).

Table 4

Agreement Levels on Select Indicators of Tik Tok Creator and Consumer Engagement

Indicator	Weighted Mean	Interpretation
1. I consider the beauty content creator's social reputation before engaging with them. If they have a good reputation, I will most likely engage with them.	3.32	Strongly Agree
2. Creator's current issues greatly impact my engagement with them.	3.33	Strongly Agree
3. If a beauty content creator is popular, I will most likely engage with them.	3.04	Agree
4. If a beauty content creator has 5k+ followers, I will most likely engage with them, even if it is the first time I have seen them.	2.83	Agree
5. I consider beauty content creator's popularity in terms of likes and followers before engaging with them.	2.94	Agree
6. I agree that more followers equate to higher customer engagement.	3.16	Agree
Overall Mean	3.10	Agree

Note. The verbal interpretation is based on the following: Strongly disagree: 1.00-1.75; Disagree: 1.76-2.50; Agree: 2.51-3.25; Strongly Agree: 3.26-4.00.

Table 5 illustrates the correlations between consumer engagement level and TikTok content, context, and creator using Spearman analysis. The results reveal significant positive relationships between consumer engagement with beauty products and TikTok content, context, and creator. TikTok context produces the highest positive correlation with consumer engagement ($\rho=0.688$, $p<0.05$), followed by TikTok content ($\rho=0.514$, $p<0.05$) and TikTok creator ($\rho=0.458$, $p<0.05$). These findings are associated with the research study of Jaakonmäki et al. (2017), which states that the main drivers of engagement are content, context, and creator, suggesting a positive relationship between consumer engagement and these variables. Given that TikTok context has the highest correlation with consumer engagement, it aligns with Bilgin's (2018) statement, implying that context is one of the most helpful marketing tools for improving consumer interaction with a product on social media.

Table 5

Correlations between Consumer Engagement and TikTok Content, Context, and Creator

Variables	Spearman rho	p-value	Decision	Relationship
Content and Consumer Engagement	0.514	0.000	Reject H_{o1}	Positive and significant
Context and Consumer Engagement	0.688	0.000	Reject H_{o2}	Positive and significant
Creator and Consumer Engagement	0.458	0.000	Reject H_{o3}	Positive and significant

Note. Correlation is computed at a five (5) percent level of significance. If the p-value is less than 0.05, there is a significant relationship; thus, reject H_o . If otherwise, there is no significant relationship.

Conclusions and Recommendations

This descriptive-correlational study investigates the influence of TikTok content, context, and creator on the engagement level of select Manila consumers with beauty products. Through an online survey, the data results show strong positive correlations between the study's dependent and independent variables, implying the necessity of considering TikTok contents, contexts, and creators in developing more engaging and effective beauty TikTok campaigns. Therefore, the researchers came up with the following recommendations for online beauty product sellers:

1. **Prioritize visually engaging demonstrations.** Videos showcasing product applications, before-and-after effects, and unboxing experiences garnered the highest agreement for engagement. Creators should prioritize visually appealing demonstrations that clearly illustrate the product's benefits and usage.

2. **Enhance with appealing text and audio.** Supplement visual demonstrations with high-quality textual descriptions and clear, relatable voice-over explanations. This approach will provide additional context and strengthen the product's message.
3. **Embrace the power of aesthetics.** Create eye-pleasing videos with high production value to enhance viewer appeal and engagement.
4. **Consider incorporating the appearance of the creator.** Many viewers responded favorably to the presence of creators in the videos. However, ensuring that the creator aligns with the brand image and target audience is crucial.
5. **Embrace creative context formats.** Experiment with unique and engaging context formats to capture viewers' attention and stand out from the competition. Consider scenarios, challenges, or storytelling approaches to present product information in a captivating manner.
6. **Partner with influencers with good social reputations.** Prioritize collaborations with creators with a positive social image and align with your brand values. This approach ensures the partnership's authenticity and resonates with your target audience.
7. **Consider the creator's previous context creativity.** Evaluate the creator's past content and promotional experience to assess their ability to develop engaging and innovative contexts for showcasing your products. For further research, it is advisable to consider topics the current study could not cover. Specifically, future researchers are recommended to:
8. **Explore diverse scenarios and examples.** Further research is needed to analyze content, context, and creator variables within various scenarios and provide specific examples for different product types and target audiences.
9. **Investigate consumer interaction motivators.** Uncover the underlying reasons behind consumers' interactions with specific content, context, and creators. This knowledge can guide creators in crafting more targeted and effective content strategies.

In conclusion, creating effective TikTok content for beauty brands in Manila requires a holistic approach encompassing high-quality content, creative context, and reputable creators. By following these recommendations, brands can increase their chances of capturing viewers' attention, driving engagement, and ultimately achieving their marketing goals.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

This section assures that the collection of data from survey participants strictly abides by the ethical standards on data privacy and security, confidentiality, and anonymity. Moreover, the study's proposal manuscript and instrument underwent an ethics review, and the researchers received an ethical clearance before data gathering.

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